

A Curious Note around the Perfect Numbers Problem

Ikorong Annouk¹ ✉

¹Research in Pure Mathematics, France

Abstract

The almost mystical regard for perfect numbers is as old as the mathematics concerning them (Hoffman, 2000; 1998). Indeed Pythagoras saw perfection in any integer that equaled the sum of all the other integers that divided evenly into it (Hoffman, 2000; 1998). More precisely, a perfect number is a positive integer that is equal to the sum of its positive divisors, excluding the number itself. The first perfect number is 6. Indeed 6 has divisors 1, 2 and 3 (excluding itself), and $1 + 2 + 3 = 6$, so 6 is a perfect number [note 28 and 496 and 33550336 are also perfect numbers (Dickson, 1919; Annouk, 2012a; 2012b; 2013; 2014; Hoffman, 2000; 1998; Yamada, 2019)]. Perfect numbers are known for some integers > 33550336 and the perfect numbers problem states that there are infinitely many perfect numbers. In this paper, we state a simple conjecture whose validity immediately implies the short proof of the perfect numbers problem via the reasoning by reduction to absurd on perfect numbers.

Keywords: *perfect numbers, perfect function.*

AMS Classification 2000: 05xx and 11xx

Prologue: This article is divided into two Sections. In Section.1, we introduce definitions that are not standard and we present some elementary properties deduced from these definitions. In Section.2, we state a simple conjecture and we show that the validity of this conjecture immediately implies the short proof of the perfect numbers problem via the reasoning by reduction to absurd on perfect numbers.

Introduction

Here, we introduce definitions that are not standard and we present some elementary properties deduced from these definitions.

Definitions 1.0 (Fundamental). For every integer $n \geq 2$, we define $\mathcal{R}(n)$, r_n and $r_{n.1}$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}(n) = \{x; 1 < x < 2n - 1 \text{ and } x \text{ is a perfect number}\}, r_n = \max_{r \in \mathcal{R}(n)} r, \text{ and } r_{n.1} = 2r_n + 6$$

(observing (use Abstract) that 6 is a perfect number, then it becomes immediate to deduce that for every integer $n \geq 4$, $6 \in \mathcal{R}(n)$ and $r_n \geq 6$ and $r_{n.1} = 2r_n + 6 \geq 18$).

Using the previous definitions, let us remark.

Remark 1.1. Let n be an integer ≥ 4 ; look at $\mathcal{R}(n)$, r_n , and $r_{n.1}$ introduced in Definitions 1.0. Then we have the following properties.

(1.1.0.) $2n - 2 \geq r_n \geq 6$; $r_{n.1} = 2r_n + 6$; $r_{n.1}$ is even, and $r_{n.1} \geq 18$.

Article History: Received: 07.07.2025 Revised: 24.07.2025 Accepted: 14.08.2025 Published: 27.08.2025

Citation: Annouk, I. (2025). A Curious Note around the Perfect Numbers Problem. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 1(4), 66-73. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1\(4\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1(4).04)

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by [AMO Publisher](#). This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

(1.1.1.) If $r_n < 2n - 4$, then: $r_n = r_{n-1}$ and $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$.

(1.1.2.) If $r_{n.1} \leq 2n$, then: $r_n < 2n - 4$ and $r_n = r_{n-1}$ and $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$.

(1.1.3) (The direct using of the perfect number). If the perfect number r_n is of the form $r_n < 2n - 4$, then $r_n = r_{n-1}$ and $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$.

(1.1.4) (The implicate using of the perfect number). If $r_{n.1} \leq 2n$, then the perfect number r_n is of the form $r_n < 2n - 4$, and $r_n = r_{n-1}$ and $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$.

Proof. Property (1.1.0) is trivial [Indeed, it suffices to use the definition of $(r_n, r_{n.1})$, and the fact that $6 \in \mathcal{R}(n)$ (notice that 6 is a perfect number (use Abstract), and observe that n is an integer ≥ 4)]. Property (1.1.1) is immediate [Indeed, if $r_n < 2n - 4$, clearly $n > 4$ (use the definition of r_n and observe that $6 \in \mathcal{R}(n)$, since n is an integer ≥ 4 and 6 is a perfect number); so

$$n > 4 \text{ and } r_n < 2n - 4 < 2n - 3 \quad (1.1)$$

(since $n > 4$ (by the previous) and $r_n < 2n - 4$ (by the hypotheses)). (1.1) immediately implies that $\mathcal{R}(n) = \mathcal{R}(n - 1)$, and therefore

$$r_n = r_{n-1} \quad (1.2)$$

Equality (1.2) immediately implies that $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$. Property (1.1.1) follows]. Property (1.1.2) is trivial [Indeed, if $r_{n.1} \leq 2n$, then using the previous inequality and the definition of $(r_{n.1}, r_n)$, it becomes trivial to deduce that

$$r_n < 2n - 4 \quad (1.3)$$

so $r_n = r_{n-1}$ and $r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$ (use inequality (1.3) and property (1.1.1)). Property (1.1.2) follows]. Property (1.1.3) is the trivial reformulation of property (1.1.1) and property (1.1.4) is an immediate reformulation of property (1.1.2). Remark 1.1 follows.

Using the definition of $(r_n, r_{n.1})$ (use Definitions 1.0), then the following remark and proposition become immediate.

Remark 1.2. If $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} r_{n.1} = +\infty$, then there are infinitely many perfect numbers. Proof. Immediate [indeed, it suffices to use the definition of $r_{n.1}$ (use Definitions 1.0)].

Proposition 1.3.

If for every integer $n \geq 4$, $r_{n.1} > 2n$ or $2n$ is a perfect number

or

there exists a perfect number $p_n > 4r_n^{r_n}$

then there are infinitely many perfect numbers.

Proof. Clearly $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} r_{n.1} = +\infty$; therefore there are infinitely many perfect numbers [use the previous equality and apply Remark 1.2].

Proposition 1.3 clearly says that: if for every integer $n \geq 4$, $r_{n.1} > 2n$ or $2n$ is a perfect number or there exists a perfect number $p_n > 4r_n^{r_n}$, then there are infinitely many perfect numbers. Proposition 1.3 is different from all the investigations that have been done on the perfect numbers problem in the past (Aiguilera, 2020; Cohen, & Williams, 1985; Gallardo, 2010; Kanold, 1956; McDaniel, & Hagis, 1975; Yamada, 2019). In Section.2, we state a simple conjecture and we show that the validity of this simple

conjecture immediately implies the short proof of the perfect numbers problem via the reasoning by reduction to absurd on perfect numbers and Proposition 1.3.

A Simple Conjecture which Immediately Implies

The Short Proof of the Perfect Numbers Problem

In this section, the definitions of $\mathcal{R}(n), r_n$ and $r_{n.1}$ (use Definitions 1.0) are crucial.

Definition 2.1 (Fundamental). (perfect function). Let \mathcal{C} be the set of all complex numbers; we say that $f(\cdot)$ is a perfect function if for every integer $n \geq 4$ and for every $r_n \in \mathcal{R}(n)$ and for every $r_{n.1}$ (use Definitions 1.0), then

$$f(r_{n.1}) = 0 \text{ if } r_{n.1} = 2n + 2; \text{ and } f(r_{n.1}) \in \mathcal{C} \setminus \{0\} \text{ otherwise.}$$

It is immediate that the definition of a perfect function gets sense (indeed for every integer $n \geq 5$ and for every $r_n \in \mathcal{R}(n)$ and for every $r_{n.1}$ (use Definitions 1.0), let $f(r_{n.1}) = (ir_{n.1} - 2in - 2i - 1)^3 + 1$ (where $i^2 = -1$); clearly $f(r_{n.1}) = 0$ if $r_{n.1} = 2n + 2$, and if $r_{n-1.1} = r_{n.1}$, then using property (1.1.2) of Remark 1.1, the reader can immediately check that $f(r_{n.1}) = f(r_{n-1.1}) = (ir_{n-1.1} - 2i(n-1) - 2i - 1)^3 + 1 = (ir_{n.1} - 2i(n-1) - 2i - 1)^3 + 1 = (ir_{n.1} - 2in - 1)^3 + 1 = 0$; so $f(r_{n.1}) = f(r_{n-1.1}) = 0$ and therefore $f(\cdot)$ define above is not a perfect function. We will see that the existence of a perfect function leads to a simple proof of the perfect numbers problem via the reasoning by reduction to absurd on perfect numbers and Proposition 1.3.

Now using the previous definition, then the following Theorem immediately implies that the existence of a perfect function immediately leads to the short proof of the perfect numbers problem.

Theorem 2.2. Let n be an integer ≥ 5 ; look at $(r_n, r_{n.1})$ (use Definitions 1.0) and suppose that there exists a perfect function $f(\cdot)$; fix once and for all such a $f(\cdot)$. Then at least one of the following three properties is satisfied by n .

(A₁). $2n$ is a perfect number or there exists a perfect number $p_n > 4r_n^{r_n}$.

(A₂). $r_{n.1} \geq 2n + 4$.

(A₃). $f(r_{n.1}) = 0$.

We are ready to give the proof of Theorem 2.2; but before, let us remark.

Remark 2.3. Let n be an integer ≥ 5 and look at $(r_n, r_{n.1})$ (use Definitions 1.0). We have the following elementary properties.

(2.3.0.) If $r_{n.1} \geq 2n + 2$, then Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n .

(2.3.1.) If $n \leq 7$, then Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n .

(2.3.2.) Let the perfect number r_n (use Definitions 1.0). If $r_n \geq 2n - 8$ and $n \geq 7$, then Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n .

(2.3.3.) Let r_n (use Definitions 1.0). If there exists a perfect number p_n such that $p_n > 4r_n^{r_n}$, then Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n .

Proof. Property (2.3.0) is trivial (indeed if $r_{n.1} \geq 2n + 2$, observing (by the definition of $r_{n.1}$) that $r_{n.1}$ is even, then the preceding inequality immediately implies that

$$r_{n,1} \geq 2n + 4 \text{ or } r_{n,1} = 2n + 2 \quad (2.0)$$

Using (2.0), then it becomes trivial to deduce that property (A_2) of Theorem 2.2 is clearly satisfied by n if $r_{n,1} \geq 2n + 4$, and property (A_3) of Theorem 2.2 is clearly satisfied by n if $r_{n,1} = 2n + 2$. Property (2.3.1) is easy (indeed, observing (by using property (1.1.0) of Remark 1.1) that $r_{n,1} \geq 18$, and remarking (via the hypotheses) that $n \leq 7$, then, using the previous two inequalities, it becomes trivial to deduce that

$$r_{n,1} \geq 2 \times 7 + 4 \geq 2n + 4 \quad (2.1)$$

so

$$r_{n,1} \geq 2n + 4 \quad (2.2)$$

(use (2.1)), and Theorem 2.2 is clearly satisfied by n (use inequality (2.2) and property (2.3.0). Property (2.3.1) follows). Property (2.3.2) is simple (indeed if $r_n \geq 2n - 8$ and $n \geq 7$, then using the preceding two inequalities coupled with the definition of ($r_n, r_{n,1}$), we immediately deduce that

$$r_{n,1} = 2r_n + 6 \geq 2(2n - 8) + 6 = 4n - 10 = 2n + 2n - 10 \geq 2n + 14 - 10 = 2n + 4 \quad (2.3)$$

Clearly

$$r_{n,1} \geq 2n + 4 \quad (2.3')$$

(use (2.3)). So Theorem 2.2 is clearly satisfied by n (use inequality (2.3') and property (2.3.0). Property (2.3.2) follows). Property (2.3.3) is trivial(indeed if there exists a perfect number p_n such that $p_n > 4r_n^{r_n}$, then property (A_1) of Theorem 2.2 is clearly satisfied by n . Property (2.3.3) follows). Remark 2.3 follows.

Using Remark 2.3, let us Remark.

Remark 2.4. Suppose that Theorem 2.2 is false; then there exists an integer $n \geq 5$ such that n does not satisfied Theorem 2.2 and n is minimum for this property.

Proof. Immediate

The previous simple remarks made, we now prove simply Theorem 2.2.

Proof of Theorem 2.2. Otherwise (we reason by reduction to absurd,) let n be a minimum counter-example to Theorem 2.2 (such a n exists [use Remark 2.4]). We observe the following.

Observation.2.2.i. Look at ($n, r_{n,1}$) (recall n is a minimum counter-example to Theorem 2.2). Then $n > 7$ and $r_{n,1} < 2n + 2$.

Clearly $n > 7$ (Otherwise $n \leq 7$ and Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n [use the previous inequality and apply property (2.3.1) of Remark 2.3]; a contradiction, since n does not satisfy Theorem 2.2); and clearly $r_{n,1} < 2n + 2$ (Otherwise

$$r_{n,1} \geq 2n + 2 \quad (2.4)$$

and using inequality (2.4) coupled with property (2.3.0) of Remark 2.3, it follows that Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n ; a contradiction, since n does not satisfy Theorem 2.2). Observation.2.2. *i* follows.

Observation.2.2.ii. Look at n and let $r_{n,1}$. Then

$$r_{n,1} \leq 2n \text{ and } r_n = r_{n-1} \text{ and } r_{n,1} = r_{n-1,1}.$$

Indeed observing (via Observation.2.2.i) that

$$r_{n.1} < 2n + 2 \tag{2.5}$$

and remarking that $r_{n.1}$ and $2n + 2$ are even ($r_{n.1}$ is even [use the definition of $r_{n.1}$] and $2n + 2$ is trivially even), then inequality (2.5) immediately implies that

$$r_{n.1} \leq 2n \tag{2.6}$$

So

$$r_n = r_{n-1} \text{ and } r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1}$$

(use inequality (2.6) and property (1.1.2) of Remark 1.1). Observation.2.2.ii follows. Observation.2.2.iii. Look at n (recall n is a minimum counter-example) and consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$). Then $2n - 2$ is not a perfect number.

Otherwise (we reason by reduction to absurd)

$$2n - 2 \text{ is a perfect number} \tag{2.7}$$

Now let the perfect number r_n (use Definitions 1.0); then using the definition of r_n and (2.7), it becomes trivial to deduce that

$$r_n = 2n - 2 \tag{2.8}$$

Equality (2.8) clearly implies that

$$r_n > 2n - 3 > 2n - 8 \tag{2.9}$$

Consequently

$$r_n > 2n - 8 \tag{2.9'}$$

(use (2.9)). Now using inequality (2.9') coupled with Observation.2.2.i (i.e. $n > 7$) and property (2.3.2) of Remark 2.3, we deduce that Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n and we have a contradiction, since n does not satisfy Theorem 2.2. Observation.2.2.iii follows.

Observation.2.2.iv. Look at n (recall n is a minimum counter-example); consider $r_{n.1}$ and look at $f(r_{n.1})$. Then $f(r_{n.1}) \neq 0$.

Immediate (Indeed notice (via Observation.2.2.ii) that $r_{n.1} \leq 2n$ and use the definition of a perfect function via the preceding equality). Observation.2.2.iv follows.

Observation.2.2.v. Look at n (recall n is a minimum counter-example) and consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$), and let the perfect number r_{n-1} (use Definitions 1.0 where n is replaced by $n - 1$). Then there exists not a perfect number p_{n-1} such that $p_{n-1} > 4r_{n-1}^{r_{n-1}}$.

Otherwise (we reason by reduction to absurd)

$$\text{Let } p_{n-1} \text{ be a perfect number such that } p_{n-1} > 4r_{n-1}^{r_{n-1}} \tag{2.10}$$

Observing (by Observation.2.2.ii) that

$$r_n = r_{n-1} \tag{2.11}$$

and using equality (2.11), it becomes trivial to deduce that (2.10) implies that

$$\text{there exists a perfect number } p_{n-1} > 4r_n^{r_n} \tag{2.12}$$

It is immediate to see that (2.12) says that

$$\text{there exists a perfect number } p_n > 4r_n^{r_n} \quad (2.13)$$

Now using (2.13) and property (2.3.3) of Remark 2.3, we deduce that Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by n and we have a contradiction, since n does not satisfy Theorem 2.2. Observation.2.2.v follows. Observation.2.2.vi. Look at n (recall n is a minimum counter-example) and consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$).

Then property (A₁) of Theorem 2.2 is not satisfied by $n - 1$.

Otherwise (we reason by reduction to absurd)

$$2(n - 1) \text{ is a perfect number or there exists a perfect number } p_{n-1} > 4r_{n-1}^{r_{n-1}} \quad (2.14)$$

(such a $2(n - 1)$ exists or such a p_{n-1} exists, since property (A₁) of Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by $n - 1$). It is trivial to see that (2.14) clearly says that

$$2n - 2 \text{ is a perfect number or there exists a perfect number } p_{n-1} > 4r_{n-1}^{r_{n-1}} \quad (2.15)$$

(2.15) immediately implies a contradiction (indeed if $2n - 2$ is a perfect number, then this contradicts Observation.2.2.iii, and if there exists a perfect number $p_{n-1} > 4r_{n-1}^{r_{n-1}}$, then the preceding inequality contradicts Observation.2.2.v). Observation.2.2.vi follows.

Observation.2.2.vii. Look at $(n, r_{n.1})$ (recall n is a minimum counter-example), and consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$).

Then property (A₂) of Theorem 2.2 is not satisfied by $n - 1$.

Otherwise (we reason by reduction to absurd)

$$r_{n-1.1} \geq 2(n - 1) + 4 \quad (2.16)$$

(inequality (2.16) exists, since property (A₂) of Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by $n - 1$). It is immediate to see that inequality (2.16) clearly says

$$r_{n-1.1} \geq 2n + 2 \quad (2.17)$$

Observing (by Observation.2.2.ii) that

$$r_{n.1} = r_{n-1.1} \quad (2.18)$$

and using equality (2.18), then we immediately deduce that inequality (2.17) clearly says that

$$r_{n.1} \geq 2n + 2 \quad (2.19)$$

Inequality (2.19) clearly contradicts Observation.2.2.ii. Observation.2.2.vii follows. Observation.2.2.viii. Look at $(n, r_{n.1})$ (recall n is a minimum counter-example to Theorem 2.2), and consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$). Then $f(r_{n.1}) = 0$.

Indeed look at n (recall n is a minimum counter-example to Theorem 2.2), and via n , consider $n - 1$ (this consideration gets sense, since $n > 7$ [use Observation.2.2.i], and so $n - 1 > 5$); then, by the minimality of n , we immediately deduce that $n - 1$ is not a counter-example to Theorem 2.2; so

$$\text{Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by } n - 1 \quad (2.20)$$

It is trivial to see that (2.20) clearly says that

at least one of property (A_j) of Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by $n - 1$; where $1 \leq j \leq 3$ (2.21)

Clearly

property (A_3) of Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by $n - 1$ (2.22)

(Indeed use (2.21) coupled with Observation.2.2.vi and Observation.2.2.vii). So

$$f(r_{n-1,1}) = 0 \quad (2.23)$$

(use (2.22) which says that property (A_3) of Theorem 2.2 is satisfied by $n - 1$). Now observing (by using Observation.2.2.ii) that $r_{n,1} = r_{n-1,1}$ and using the preceding equality, we easily deduce that (2.23) clearly says that $f(r_{n,1}) = 0$. Observation.2.2.viii follows.

These simple observations made, then it becomes trivial to deduce that Observation.2.2.viii contradicts Observation.2.2.iv. Theorem 2.2 follows.

Theorem 2.2 immediately implies that, **If there exists a perfect function (see Definition 2.1), then there are infinitely many perfect numbers.**

Theorem 2.5. If there exists a perfect function, then there are infinitely many perfect numbers.

Proof. Use Theorem 2.2 and Proposition 1.3.

Using Theorem 2.5, then it becomes natural and not surprising to conjecture the following.

Conjecture. The set \mathcal{P} is the set of all perfect function; then $\mathcal{P} \neq \emptyset$.

References

- Aguilera, C. (2020). Notes on perfect numbers [Preprint]. HAL archives-ouvertes.
- Annouk, I. (2012a). A curious synopsis on the Goldbach conjecture, the perfect numbers, the Mersenne composite numbers and the Sophie Germain primes. *General Mathematics Journal*, 20(2–3).
- Annouk, I. (2012b). Nice rendez vous with primes and composite numbers. *South Asian Journal of Mathematics*, 2(4), 430–439.
- Annouk, I. (2013). Meeting with primes and composite numbers. *Asian Journal of Mathematics and Applications*.
- Annouk, I. (2014). Then we characterize primes and composite numbers via divisibility. *International Journal of Advanced in Pure Mathematical Sciences*, 2(1).
- Cohen, G. L., & Williams, R. J. (1985). Extensions of some results concerning odd perfect numbers. *Fibonacci Quarterly*, 23(1), 70–76.
- Dickson, L. E. (1919). *History of the Theory of Numbers* (Vol. I, p. 4). Washington, DC: Carnegie Institution of Washington.
- Dickson, L. E. (1919). *History of the Theory of Numbers* (Vol. I, p. 10). Washington, DC: Carnegie Institution of Washington.
- Gallardo, L. H. (2010). On a remark of Makowski about perfect numbers. *Elemente der Mathematik*, 65(121), 121–126.
- Hoffman, P. (1998). *The man who loved only numbers: The story of Paul Erdős and the search for mathematical truth* (pp. 30–49).

- Hoffman, P. (2000). *Erdős, l'homme qui n'aimait que les nombres* (pp. 30–49). Paris: Éditions Belin. (Translated from the 1998 English version)
- Kanold, H. J. (1956). Eine Bemerkung über die Menge der vollkommenen Zahlen. *Mathematische Annalen*, 131(4), 390–392.
- McDaniel, W. L., & Hagsis, P., Jr. (1975). Some results concerning the non-existence of odd perfect numbers of the form $p^\alpha M^{2\beta}$. *Fibonacci Quarterly*, 13(1), 25–28.
- Yamada, T. (2019). A new upper bound for odd perfect numbers of a special form. *Colloquium Mathematicum*, 156(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.4064/cm8060-12-2019>

